
Detection of Forest fire using Image Classification

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ABSTRACT:

The paper describes the idea used to detect forest fire based on video processing. The basic idea is to detect fire in forest areas where frequent attention is needed. Using cameras in forests with video processing will help to detect fire and can be used as a caution system for fire fighters. Based on the dataset that has been provided, the algorithm uses supervised learning method to train a model and detect fire in the input image using the trained model. The system also provides the accuracy of the prediction ranges from 0 to 100. Experimental results show that the developed method can achieve fully automatic surveillance of forest fire. These kind of system provide more accuracy than traditional fire detection sensors and can cover larger areas using a single camera. The accuracy of the model can also be improved by providing more number of input images that can be trained for classification.

Keywords: Image classification, Forest fire, Tensorflow, Neural Network

Introduction:

As technology grows everyday artificial intelligence is being an essential part in everyday tasks as it has more potential than others. The fields like machine learning and deep learning and their subsets have an immense growth. The training of the models using the algorithms and classifiers requires huge amount of data to analyze them and to extract features. The focus of classification process is to group all the pixels from a digital image into classes. Normally the numerical data in each pixel is used for classification of an image. The goal of image classification is to identify the unique features occurring in image in terms of object that actually represent on the ground. Classifying between the objects is a difficult task and therefore image classification is a crucial task in the field of digital image processing.

The term image classification refers to labelling of images into fixed classes. There can be n number of classes in which the input image can be categorized. Classifying the image manually may be a hardest task when there is a huge amount of data to be classified but that can be handed over to a machine that can automate the entire process using computer vision. This approach can be used in any fields where humans need to spend more time supervising a work. The development in the field of autonomous driving is a great example of application of image classification.

From our case study forest fire doesn't only affect the forest but it also affects the flora and fauna that poses a serious threat to the bio diversity. There are two main causes for forest fire. One is man-made causes and the other is natural causes. Both of them not only affects the forests but also the ecology. Existing fire detection system uses the combination of infrared and ultraviolet sensors to detect fire and there are some researches done by many scholars. A paper named early fire-detection method based on image processing describes the use of sensors to detect fire. The paper describes the use of RGB values that has been converted from the given input video feed to detect fire but sometimes RGB values can differ and it may not detect the fire accurately. Forest fires should be taken in a serious manner to avoid loss of valuable timbers and to avoid global warming. Our proposed method uses supervised learning process in which the machines are trained using well "labelled" training data, and on basis of that data, machines predict the output by creating a supervised model. The labelled data are those which has the training and testing images of forest fire and images of green forest that has no fire.

Image Classification

In machine learning Supervised learning is a type where the models are trained using data that is labelled for training and testing purpose. With using the data the machine will predict the output for the given input data. A labelled data is nothing but the data that is marked with correct output. In this method the data that is used as training data will work as a controller that tells the machine to predict the correct output. It is defined as a the construction of building where the workers work under the supervision of the builder. It is a overall process of providing the data as input with the correct output data to the classification model. The main focus of supervised learning is to find a mapping function to map the (x) that is the input function and (y) that is the output function.

In this method of learning the models are trained using dataset that are labelled before, Then the model learns about the data using the labels. After the completion of the training using the labelled data the model is tested on the test data. There are two types of image classification, Single label image classification and Multi label image classification.

2.1 Single Label Classification

Single label image classification is the most common method of supervised learning for image classification. In this method a only one label or an annotation is present for each image and the output of the model will be a single output for each input image. The output from our trained model is a vector of length that is equal to the number of classes and some values denoting the score that the image belongs to this class. The softmax function is used to add the score to one and the total score is taken from the output. Softmax helps to bound the output between zero and one. Single label classification can predict multiple classes where there are more than one or two classes or binary classes, in which there will be two classes.

$$\sigma(\vec{z})_i = \frac{e^{z_i}}{\sum_{j=1}^K e^{z_j}}$$

2.2 Multi Label Classification

Multi label classification is the supervised learning method in which two or more number of labels can be in a image. Multi label classification is still used in the medical field where the x-ray shows the number of disease that a patient have.

2.3 Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional neural network is also known as CNN is an artificial neural network that is most popularly used for classification problems. Image classification mostly uses CNN but other types of data can also be classified. CNN forms a neural network and it is special in finding the patterns in the data and use to predict output. Those patterns are very useful for image classification.

Fig 1 – Convolutional Neural Network

Convolutional neural network have hidden layers called convolutional layers and these layers make the CNN. It may not have convolutional layers but the base of CNN is the convolutional layers. The convolutional layer receives the input and transforms it into another form and sends the data to the next layer. Getting and transforming the input into another form is called convolutional operation. As discussed earlier convolutional neural network detect patterns form images precisely so that it is used to predict output. In each convolutional layer we should apply filters to detect patterns. Patterns are nothing but the features in the image like the edges, shapes, corners etc are used with filters. A filter is nothing but a small matrix and the row and column of the matrix will be determined by the user. The matrix is first initialized with random digits. Now the convolutionallayer with a filter will be a 3x3 filter. When the input is given to the convolutional layer the filter slides through the dimension of the image with the 3x3 filter and this process is known as convolving.

0.927	0.456	0.986
0.234	0.523	0.765
0.198	0.220	0.341

Fig 2 – Matrix example

At first the input image is taken from the input layer and then the filter slides through every pixels and forms a dot product with the matrix formed. The matrix of the dot product will be the output of the matrix. This matrix will be passed to the next layer as input and the same process with the filter will be done in the next layer and forms the output. The filters now can be mentioned as pattern detectors as it creates patterns from the input.

Proposed Method

Our proposed method is based on single-label classification and uses Tensorflow to make the classification of fire. Tensorflow is an open source end-to-end platform for machine learning. The dataset that we use has 1000 images of forest fire and 1000 images of green forest in the dimension of 640x480 pixels and in three RGB channels to train the model and we will do the classification in 2 categories. Below are the examples for images that have been used for training.

Fig 3 – Forest Fire Dataset

Our dataset contains 1000 images of forest fire used for training the sequential model.

Fig 4 –Green Forest Dataset

Necessary libraries like Tensorflow and Numpy are imported at first. The data is then splitted into training and testing data. The data is divided like 80% of data is used to train the model and 20% of the data is used to test the trained model. As we have only two classes to classify the image for detection of fire in forest or not so the labels for the model is 2, First label is Fire_Detected and the second label is No_Fire_Detected. The dataset is first configured for performance so that buffered prefetching is used so the data can be yielded from the disk without blocking the I/O blocking. The RGB values of each pixels are standardized between 0 to 1 as the range from 0 to 255 is not ideal for a convolutional neural network. Our model

consists of three convolutional blocks with max pooling layer in each of the convolutional block and there will be a fully connected layer with 128 units and that is activated by a ReLU activation function. Our model is tuned to provide high accuracy. Adam optimizer is used to loss function is used to find the metrics. After successfully configuring the model it is now trained with epochs of 10 and the training results are plotted.

Fig 5 – Validation Accuracy

Now the results shows that our accuracy is at 60% with the validation of the data. From the above plot we can see that the training accuracy is increasing linearly over time but validation accuracy is settled at 60%. When we use small amount of data for training the model will learn from the noise and unwanted details from the given data which may lead to decreased in performance while testing the model. This situation is known as overfitting. To overcome over fitting we will use data augmentation to produce more training data as overfitting occurs only when there is less number of training data. Data augmentation produces more training data from the given set of data by augmenting them using random transformation methods that will output some realistic images like the input. This will help our model to train on more data and overcome the overfitting phenomenon. After data augmentation is completed the model is again trained with epochs of 15 and the results of our new model is plotted.

Fig 6 –Validation accuracy after data augmentation

After data augmentation we can see significant improvement in the validation accuracy of the model. The validation accuracy is now gained additional 10 to 15% that will be enough for the model for predicting on new data.

Result and Discussion

After the training of model, it is then tested among various images to check if it detects fire accurately. The plots shows the 75% accuracy on training the model. But it can be tested only on real scenario. So for testing 2 images are loaded and classified using our trained model to classify fire. Below are the results

Fig 7 – Fire detected by our model

Fig 7 shows that our model successfully detected fire in the image and prints accordingly on the image. As our training data contains images of forest fire so our model can detect fire in testing image.

Fig 8 – Fire not detected by our model

In the above figure Fig 8 our model has not detected any fire in the image so it prints that no_fire_detected. Our dataset contains images of green forest and trained on those images so it detected that there is no fire on the given image. As of now we are loading the image one by one but we can direct a webcam feed to our model to detect fire in a forest on a real-time basis.

CONCLUSION:

The research proposes a forest fire detection system. By using the Convolutional Neural Network and Image classification we did a classifier that can detect forest fire with great accuracy. Usage of sensors can give a false signal over a normal fire even on a match stick, but our model is capable of detecting only forest fire. As of now only 1000 images is used to train the model. In future more number of images can be used for training for more accurate results. By fixing a camera over a distance and performing the algorithm will result in detection of forest fire in great way.

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